

JAVASCRIPT-DA OB'EKTLARNI YARATISH VA ULARGA KIRISH

Anvarjonova Mahliyo Minavvarjon qizi

Qo'qon davlat pedagogika instituti

Fizika – matematika fakulteti

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu tezisda ob'ektlarni qanday yaratish, ob'ektlarning xossalari va usullarini qo'shish va o'zgartirish, shuningdek ularga qanday kirish mumkinligi muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zi: JavaScript, ob'ektlar.

Аннотация: В этой тезис обсуждается, как создавать объекты, добавлять и изменять свойства и методы объекта, а также как получить к ним доступ.

Ключевые слова: JavaScript, объекты.

Abstract: This thesis discusses how to create objects, add and modify object properties and methods, and how to access them.

Keywords: JavaScript, objects.

JavaScript - bu interaktiv veb-sahifalarni yaratish uchun tez-tez ishlatiladigan dasturlash tili. JavaScript -dagi hamma narsa ob'ekt, jumladan raqamlar va satrlar kabi ibtidoiy ma'lumotlar turlari. Ob'ektlar - bu funktsiyalar yoki boshqa ob'ektlar bo'lishi mumkin bo'lgan xususiyatlar to'plami. JavaScript -da ob'ekt yaratish jingalak qavslar {} ichiga olingan va vergul bilan ajratilgan xususiyatlar va ularning qiymatlari ro'yxatini o'z ichiga olgan literal ob'ekt yordamida amalga oshirilishi mumkin. Masalan :

```
let myObj = {  
  name: "John",  
  age: 30,  
  city: "New York"  
};
```

Ob'ektning xususiyatlariga nuqta belgilari yoki kvadrat qavslar yordamida kirish mumkin. Masalan :

```
let myName = myObj.name; // получить значение свойства name объекта myObj  
let myAge = myObj["age"]; // получить значение свойства age объекта myObj
```

Bundan tashqari, konstruktor funksiyasi yoki klassi yordamida ob'ektlarni yaratishingiz mumkin, bu sizga bir xil xususiyat va usullarga ega bo'lgan bir nechta ob'ekt namunalari yaratishga imkon beradi.

Masalan, konstruktor funksiyasi quyidagicha ko'rinishi mumkin:

```
function Person(name, age, city) {  
  this.name = name;  
  this.age = age;  
  this.city = city;  
}
```

```
let person1 = new Person("John", 30, "New York"); // создать новый экземпляр объекта Person
```

```
let person2 = new Person("Jane", 25, "Los Angeles"); // создать новый экземпляр объекта Person
```

nomi, yoshi va shahar xususiyatlari uchun o'z qiymatlariga ega.

JavaScript- da ob'ektlarni qanday yaratish va ularga kirishning kichik bir ko'rinishi .
 Qo'shimcha savollaringiz bo'lsa, iltimos, bemalol so'rang!

JavaScript -dagi ob'ektlar o'zgaruvchan bo'lishi mumkin, ya'ni ular yaratilgandan keyin ularning xususiyatlari va usullarini o'zgartirishingiz mumkin. Masalan :

```
let myObj = {
  name: "John",
  age: 30,
  city: "New York"
};
myObj.age = 31; // изменить значение свойства age объекта myObj
```

Bundan tashqari, istalgan vaqtda ob'ektga faqat nomi bilan murojaat qilish va yangi xususiyat yoki usulni ko'rsatish orqali ob'ektlarga yangi xususiyatlar va usullarni qo'shishingiz mumkin. Masalan :

```
let myObj = {
  name: "John",
  age: 30,
  city: "New York"
};
myObj.gender = "male"; // добавить новое свойство gender объекта myObj
myObj.sayHello = function() {
  console.log("Hello!");
}; // добавить новый метод sayHello объекта myObj
```

Bundan tashqari, ob'ektlar ichki joylashtirilishi mumkin, ya'ni siz boshqa ob'ektlarni xususiyat sifatida o'z ichiga olgan ob'ektlarga ega bo'lishingiz mumkin. Masalan :

```
let myObj = {
  name: "John",
  age: 30,
  address: {
    street: "123 Main St",
    city: "New York",
    state: "NY"
  }
};
let myStreet = myObj.address.street; // получить значение свойства street объекта address в объекте myObj
```

JavaScript- dagi ob'ektlar bilan nima qilishingiz mumkinligining kichik bir qismidir . Ular ma'lumotlarni saqlash va boshqarish, sinflar yaratish va boshqalar uchun ishlatilishi mumkin. Ushbu dasturlash tili bilan muvaffaqiyatli ishlash uchun JavaScript- da ob'ektlarni qanday yaratish va ularga kirishni bilish muhimdir .

Xulosa

Ushbu tezisda JavaScript dasturlash tilida ob'ektlarni qanday yaratish, ularning xossalari va usullarini qo'shish va o'zgartirish hamda ularga qanday kirish mumkinligi batafsil yoritilgan. JavaScript-dagi ob'ektlar ma'lumotlarni saqlash va manipulyatsiya qilish, sinflar va boshqa ma'lumotlar tuzilmalarini yaratish uchun muhim vositadir.

JavaScript-dagi ob'ektlarni tushunish ushbu dasturlash tili bilan muvaffaqiyatli ishlash uchun juda muhimdir..

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